

DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MANAGERS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION DIDACTIC SUPPLY

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Abstract In the article, the theoretical foundations of didactic support for the formation of information competence in distance education, the structure of didactic support of distance education and automated didactic support were developed. A sample content of electronic resources and a graphic display of information, which serve to form the information competence of future specialists in the conditions of distance education, have been developed.

Key words: Information competence, distance education, dualism, relativity, systematicity, selectivity, accumulation, polyfunctionality, mental cards, modern electronic resources.

In the formation of information competence of future specialists in the distance education environment, it is necessary to clarify its main features and functions. Based on the analysis of scientific research and educational literature, we recommend including the following in the characteristics of information competence:

dualism - existence of objective (external assessment of information competence) and subjective (internal - self-assessment of information competence by a person) sides;

relativity - taking into account the obsolescence of knowledge and knowledge bases, they can be considered new only conditionally in a certain space-time interval;

systematicity - the existence of a unique knowledge or knowledge base in each person;

selectivity - not turning all the information received by a person into a base of knowledge and knowledge;

accumulation - knowledge accumulates over time and becomes a knowledge base;

self-development - emergence of new knowledge through creative thinking based on the knowledge base;

"polyfunctionality" - multi-functionality of information (knowledge) in the knowledge base related to different subjects.

We can include such functions as cognitive, communicative, adaptive, normative, evaluation, interactive functions of information competence. These functions are inextricably linked to each other and can be exchanged from one to another, but represent a single process. This reflects the interdependence between the problems of several disciplines.

The characteristics and functions of the category of information competence create the necessary conditions for creating its didactic support in the distance education environment.

In distance education, the role of the teacher in the teaching process is expanded and updated.

Now the teacher is required to coordinate the learning process, regularly improve the subject he is teaching in accordance with news and innovations, deepen his level and creative activity.

The teacher will have the opportunity to adjust the educational materials and content depending on the personal characteristics and abilities of each student. This will certainly increase the effectiveness of education.

Therefore, this factor has found its place in the following main characteristics of distance education:

communicative component and its implementation;

delivery of educational materials, correct selection and justification of its content;

the existence of a system for ensuring the flexibility of the educational content to the student's personal characteristics and abilities.

The development of distance education places high demands on the design of the educational process, its quality, and the correct implementation of didactic support of all stages of teaching on the basis of distance education.

Didactic provision of distance education means a teaching-methodological complex created on the basis of the systematic principle of MT in a specific subject or subject department.

When creating educational methodological complexes, first of all, it is necessary to take into account factors that take into account the system of certain principles of didactics (S.I. Arkhangelsky, Y.K. Babansky, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, I.Y. Lerner, V.A. Slastenin, P.I. Pidkasistiy) and the features of distance education.

It is considered appropriate to take the following principles as the main ones in the formation of the educational and methodological base of distance education: didactic usefulness; sequence and systematicity; modularity; multilevel; cognitive; flexibility; non-linear content.

Among the above principles, the most important one is didactic usefulness, because other principles are formed on the basis of this principle and complement it.

Didactic utility is a feature of didactic support aimed at the development of the student's personality in achieving the set educational goal. This is with the possibility of forming the content of the educational content, taking into account the psychophysiological characteristics and age of the student, as well as the requirements of the social activity of the knowledge system. is determined.

The content and structure of didactic support of distance education should be created and implemented based on the above principles and determine the content of the technology of distance education. Different methods are used to create didactic support. We can divide the functional basis of the didactic supply structure into the following two parts:

substantive and managerial.

intellectual communication.

MT denies direct contact with the teacher. The model of teaching and emotional-intellectual communication is replaced by the teaching model, which is the basis of the teacher program. The MT teaching model consists of an information-science environment, which includes various types of educational materials, software for educational purposes, and a student activity management model.

Automated didactic support is required in distance education.

Automatic didactic support consists of 2 components: didactic and functional support.

Didactic support consists of teaching-methodical sets on specific subject content.

Functional support - allows to model the learning of educational content and consists of pedagogical and technological parts.

Pedagogical - methodical sequence of goal- and person-oriented pedagogical methods and technologies to achieve the pedagogical goal.

Technological - a sequence of information technologies used to achieve a pedagogical goal. The participation of the teacher in the creation of the technological part makes it possible to combine pedagogical and information technologies.

The analysis of practical experiences in the creation of teaching-methodical complexes provides an opportunity to generalize the automated didactic system and determine its stages. From a pedagogical point of view, the stages of creating an automated didactic system show that it is an important factor, and it mainly consists of the following 2 project activities: pedagogical and technological. Together, they make up the functional support of the system and are a model for designing a didactic system.

The functional support has a dynamic structure, which reflects the processes, stages of the automatic didactic system, the procedure for creating the automatic didactic support (ADT), and these blocks are directed to obtain the intended results.

Electronic resources are the main didactic support of distance education. The term "resource" is currently used in a very broad sense. "Educational resource" means a source of educational materials in various forms and forms used for learning during the educational process. In other words, an educational resource is a source of information used in the educational process. Based on the above, we can divide educational resources into the following groups:

1. Traditional publication materials containing text, pictures, diagrams and tables (textbook, study guide, text of lectures and courses, manuals for laboratory and practical exercises, problems collection, dictionaries, catalogs, reference books, handouts, educational materials, various methodological manuals and instructions, questions and tasks, etc.).

2. Traditional audio and video materials: musical and speech materials (discs with lectures, audiobooks, educational video films, etc.), demonstration videos, presentation films, cinematographic products.

3. Modern (digital) electronic resources: files recorded on various media (disks, flash drives, etc.), digital electronic materials made possible to hear and see information of groups 1 and 2 using modern household electronic devices or computers.

4. Special programs for studying, independent education and checking the acquired knowledge: programs, programs that highlight the educational content and are directed to interaction with the student and are designed to solve certain pedagogical tasks set or systems.

The third group of resources intended for storage and distribution is mainly traditional print and audio-video materials transformed into electronic forms intended for hearing and viewing with the help of modern computer techniques.

According to the format of storage and presentation of information, electronic resources can be classified as follows:

separate files - file equivalents of traditional resources of group 1 (text documents with tables and graphic illustrations, graphic files of illustrations, files in audio-video format, etc.).

hypertext materials - electronic educational literature consisting of elements of electronic educational literature, such as text, graphics, multimedia elements, and electronic equivalent of traditional resources of groups 1-2.

Among the electronic resources, the "traditional educational resource", that is, a special teacher's programming tool, plays an important role. An example of the most common such resource is electronic testing software

Resources in groups 3 and 4 are collectively called "E-learning resources". The creation of the following software electronic equivalent of 1-2 groups of resources plays an important role in the automation of the educational process in the distance education system: computer training programs; computer textbooks and training manuals; automated teaching system for the studied subject; automatic knowledge test control system; computer simulators;

auxiliary tools (programs that provide a visual environment for performing laboratory work, using computer encyclopedias and dictionaries; automated training courses.

Electronic educational resources means a system of transmission (delivery) of educational materials combined with a system of automatic control of acquired knowledge, which allows automatic adjustment taking into account the personal characteristics of the user, that is, the student.

The following methods can be used to illuminate information based on graphic schemes: clusters, metal cards, fish skeleton scheme, denotation graphs, etc.

The phrase "cluster" is derived from the English word "Cluster", which can be used to systematically illuminate a large amount of information.

Mental cards were developed by Tony Bzen, a well-known author, speaker and consultant on the psychology of learning and thinking. It is derived from the word Mind maps and is also known as "Intellect-card" or "Mind card". Also, educational materials include fish skeleton, jigsaw, FSMU, boomerang, scarab, cascade, Veyer, pirbord, "T-scheme-technique", delphi, blitz-survey, "Why?" technologies, BBXB (I know, I want to know, I have learned), conceptual table, explanation on the basis of the insert table enables the distance education student to receive information well and learn it easily.

Formation of information competence in future specialists in distance learning environment is different from traditional educational environment. As an organizer of didactic support, web quest tasks also play an important role in this. A web quest is a problem-oriented activity in which students retrieve information from Internet resources. It should be noted that the Internet resources are very wide and unlimited. In such an environment, students will be able to deviate from the set topic, get various unnecessary information and spend a lot of time on the process of obtaining information. However, the formation process of information competence is not only about obtaining and storing information, but it is also evaluated by the formation of the skills of reading, understanding, understanding and creative processing, practical use of this information.

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